

Appendix B: List of *XMM-Newton* observations

In Table B.1 is the comprehensive journal of all *XMM-Newton* observations of the X-HESS AGN. For each source, we report their observation(s) with the corresponding X-HESS and *XMM-Newton* identifier, the starting date, as well as both the net exposure and counts in the broadband $E = 0.3 - 10$ keV observer-frame energy interval.

The hyphens reported in the same table indicate that the corresponding EPIC pn/MOS1/MOS2 observations are either unavailable or excluded from the analysis according to the procedure described in § 3.2.

Table B.1: Journal of observations.

ID	Obs. No.	Obs. ID	Start Date	Exp	Cts _{tot}
(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
1	1	0150970101	2003-05-07	-/9.7/9.7	-/69/53
1	2	0150970301	2003-12-02	17.0/23.4/23.4	577/192/203
1	3	0671540201	2011-11-04	13.5/21.0/21.0	398/159/123
1	4	0671540301	2011-11-06	20.8/25.0/25.1	1150/408/362
1	5	0671540401	2011-11-21	17.5/23.4/24.0	610/178/182
1	6	0671540501	2011-11-27	17.4/22.0/22.0	518/184/188
1	7	0671540601	2011-12-01	13.2/19.7/20.2	582/181/178
1	8	0671540701	2011-12-04	2.7/6.6/9.4	69/32/46
1	9	0743950101	2014-10-31	23.9/64.3/62.2	1348/952/750
1	10	0743950201	2014-11-03	32.6/57.7/56.4	1020/462/384
1	11	0743950301	2014-11-05	20.7/33.5/31.2	954/422/369
1	12	0743950401	2014-11-21	38.6/53.3/53.3	894/288/233
1	13	0743950501	2014-11-23	39.3/57.1/-	682/251/-
1	14	0743950601	2014-11-25	46.9/60.7/60.8	1743/499/391
1	15	0743950701	2014-11-27	44.1/61.0/58.6	2302/655/525
2	1	0112521001	2002-04-10	-/10.0/10.0	-/143/154
2	2	0112521101	2002-04-16	7.6/9.7/9.6	409/102/136
2	3	0200980101	2004-09-26	70.3/102.3/103.0	3837/1488/1773
2	4	0657802001	2011-03-24	3.2/5.6/8.3	45/36/22
2	5	0657801601	2011-04-17	2.1/4.3/4.8	61/48/34
2	6	0657801801	2011-09-26	12.4/-/15.7	342/-/137
2	7	0657802201	2011-11-23	12.9/15.9/15.9	234/109/101
2	8	0693850801	2012-10-23	6.0/8.4/8.7	193/88/97
2	9	0693850901	2012-10-25	7.1/13.6/13.6	316/174/179
2	10	0693851001	2012-10-27	3.9/10.2/11.1	109/82/97
2	11	0693851701	2012-11-12	-/9.5/9.4	-/62/63
2	12	0693851801	2012-11-14	6.8/8.8/8.8	201/69/85
2	13	0693851101	2012-11-16	2.9/4.9/5.0	66/48/56
3	1	0112521901	2002-05-31	10.3/15.0/14.9	30/12/14
3	2	0142830101	2003-11-30	90.0/101.8/102.3	387/83/115
3	3	0744010101	2014-12-28	-/-/51.1	-/-/35
3	4	0744010201	2014-12-30	-/-/20.1	-/-/17
3	5	0824610101	2018-12-13	83.5/-/104.2	130/-/47
3	6	0824610201	2018-12-19	59.9/-/-	100/-/-
3	7	0824610301	2018-12-31	-/-/81.9	-/-/26
3	8	0824610401	2019-01-02	-/-/110.2	-/-/42
4	1	0693380301	2013-05-13	-/28.3/28.4	-/240/273
4	2	0693380501	2013-06-20	13.2/16.2/16.2	743/244/224
4	3	0727960701	2013-11-14	15.2/25.3/25.1	1357/624/652
4	4	0727960801	2013-11-16	11.1/18.4/18.2	1659/708/594
4	5	0764850201	2015-05-31	46.9/59.7/59.3	1597/483/542
4	6	0764850301	2015-12-12	23.5/33.1/31.8	796/309/254
4	7	0764850401	2015-12-24	9.5/14.2/14.2	248/99/88
5	1	0124712501	2002-06-07	-/27.7/27.7	-/143/127
5	2	0204040101	2004-06-06	-/77.4/77.2	-/74/97
5	3	0204040201	2004-06-18	-/-/54.2	-/-/78
5	4	0204040301	2004-07-12	46.6/-/-	178/-/-

Continuation of Table B.1

ID	Obs. No.	Obs. ID	Start Date	Exp	Cts _{tot}
(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
5	5	0304320301	2005-06-27	26.1/-/-	562/-/-
5	6	0304320201	2005-06-28	58.7/-/-	1542/-/-
5	7	0304320801	2006-06-06	35.9/-/-	161/-/-
6	1	0093030301	2003-08-15	-/4.9/5.0	-/34/46
6	2	0093031001	2003-08-29	1.9/5.1/4.3	34/23/24
6	3	0093031101	2003-09-06	-/2.7/2.8	-/23/27
6	4	0093031401	2003-10-08	-/3.1/3.2	-/61/92
6	5	0093031501	2003-10-10	1.6/4.2/4.3	63/86/75
6	6	0693180901	2012-08-07	24.2/-/-	2557/-/-
7	1	0150470601	2003-07-15	-/37.9/25.7	-/248/125
7	2	0690870101	2013-07-20	15.9/19.3/19.3	197/78/78
7	3	0690870501	2013-08-10	-/101.3/101.3	-/451/381
7	4	0743830501	2015-01-13	-/117.1/116.4	-/617/595
7	5	0743830601	2015-01-25	-/110.2/110.4	-/661/659
8	1	0110890301	2002-06-22	17.9/20.9/21.0	1009/365/363
8	2	0300470101	2005-07-18	79.1/-/-	704/-/-
8	3	0743050301	2015-01-19	134.9/-/-	982/-/-
8	4	0743050801	2015-01-21	111.3/-/-	876/-/-
9	1	0763450301	2017-07-18	114.6/-/-	477/-/-
9	2	0784030101	2017-07-21	17.3/21.3/21.4	78/26/20
9	3	0784030501	2017-08-04	17.4/21.7/20.9	72/17/20
9	4	0784030601	2017-08-15	-/22.3/22.2	-/30/8
10	1	0763450301	2017-07-18	114.5/-/-	541/-/-
10	2	0784030101	2017-07-21	17.3/21.3/21.4	100/29/21
10	3	0784030501	2017-08-04	17.4/21.7/20.9	84/18/14
10	4	0784030601	2017-08-15	17.7/22.3/22.2	84/44/43
11	1	0153220401	2003-02-08	2.4/8.6/8.9	661/628/678
11	2	0505050201	2007-06-09	4.5/9.1/9.3	1685/933/864
11	3	0505050701	2007-06-15	6.2/10.2/9.3	2255/974/884
11	4	0505050301	2007-06-17	-/14.7/14.4	-/1157/1277
12	1	0305750401	2005-06-23	2.7/-/6.0	23/-/16
12	2	0741580101	2014-12-04	9.4/12.1/12.1	269/97/106
12	3	0764910201	2015-10-23	33.1/51.4/48.8	430/222/191
12	4	0792790101	2016-10-12	48.0/-/68.0	961/-/446
13	1	0804560101	2017-05-14	21.5/30.0/32.5	18706/5356/6060
13	2	0804560201	2017-05-15	17.0/23.4/23.4	577/192/203
13	3	0823090301	2018-11-21	6.7/9.4/10.1	8801/2818/2774
14	1	0094310101	2002-11-18	56.7/64.6/64.3	533/230/221
14	2	0094310201	2002-12-15	59.9/71.5/72.2	803/393/365
14	3	0673000142	2011-12-07	2.4/4.2/4.2	99/51/32
15	1	0094310101	2002-11-18	57.0/64.5/64.3	457/118/128
15	2	0094310201	2002-12-15	60.2/71.4/72.1	445/119/143
16	1	0677590132	2011-07-23	11.0/12.4/12.4	893/285/252
16	2	0820080401	2019-01-11	9.2/-/-	146/-/-
17	1	0551850101	2008-10-17	34.2/51.9/53.4	380/157/209
17	2	0551851201	2009-03-21	-/79.1/79.0	-/184/212
18	1	0556560101	2008-12-10	26.9/-/-	946/-/-
18	2	0764100501	2015-11-21	20.3/-/-	676/-/-
19	1	0722670301	2014-01-09	39.7/-/-	379/-/-
19	2	0722670601	2014-01-13	27.9/-/-	330/-/-

Continuation of Table B.1

ID	Obs. No.	Obs. ID	Start Date	Exp	Cts _{tot}
(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
20	1	0051760201	2001-06-18	13.4/17.8/17.1	5915/1886/2048
20	2	0763480101	2016-01-25	39.8/60.3/60.1	12120/3387/3092
21	1	0152660101	2003-02-08	17.8/21.1/21.1	66454/19520/19243
21	2	0781430101	2017-01-24	76.3/107.2/110.0	149871/46126/46036
22	1	0673002332	2012-05-25	3.7/4.2/4.2	529/216/188
22	2	0673002333	2012-05-25	-/4.2/4.2	-/97/106
23	1	0553230201	2008-12-30	51.0/60.8/60.5	333/120/92
24	1	0673750101	2011-12-24	18.1/22.4/22.4	1863/593/563
25	1	0673770301	2012-07-02	28.6/39.0/38.9	407/153/144
26	1	0762870301	2016-02-05	19.0/25.2/26.9	1056/389/365
27	1	0677640138	2012-01-12	10.9/12.4/12.4	702/190/210
28	1	0037982701	2002-08-15	11.9/17.5/17.8	765/262/278
29	1	0402320101	2007-02-02	4.9/6.2/6.4	1207/366/367
30	1	0780320101	2016-09-02	-/15.4/16.4	-/261/298
31	1	0152530101	2002-10-05	18.8/27.7/28.0	1475/665/594
32	1	0728990101	2014-10-04	45.5/55.0/55.0	9109/2909/2914
33	1	0821730301	2019-04-27	17.6/22.2/22.6	1162/441/445
34	1	0742570101	2015-04-09	54.0/-/62.4	793/-/231
35	1	0302581801	2005-10-10	19.2/-/28.0	2163/-/707
36	1	0803950601	2017-11-17	15.2/19.7/21.9	1703/559/699
37	1	0300910301	2005-10-08	22.0/29.5/30.5	22801/6724/8556
38	1	0802220601	2017-12-04	9.6/12.5/12.5	1444/449/479
39	1	0411980301	2006-11-01	4.2/6.5/6.5	2237/719/809
40	1	0843830301	2019-05-14	13.0/19.4/19.5	1831/505/469
41	1	0783520201	2016-05-04	17.6/21.4/21.4	3797/1251/1216
42	1	0802200801	2017-11-28	23.6/-/34.6	578/-/264
43	1	0843830501	2019-05-05	13.7/16.8/16.8	999/269/270
44	1	0145750101	2003-06-23	22.0/29.7/29.8	902/280/289
45	1	0083000301	2001-12-15	-/30.6/30.8	-/387/380
46	1	0103863201	2002-12-19	4.5/8.4/8.4	576/275/290
47	1	0822530201	2018-05-28	29.3/35.1/35.1	1568/396/477
48	1	0843830901	2019-07-05	10.8/16.4/16.4	948/321/331
49	1	0033540601	2002-05-11	5.9/7.4/7.4	574/159/168
50	1	0306680201	2005-11-29	4.2/5.0/5.0	616/233/239
51	1	0143150201	2003-06-18	20.2/27.2/27.3	4093/1516/1496
52	1	0801790601	2017-06-18	22.0/27.0/27.2	1307/384/424
53	1	0304570101	2006-04-20	8.5/11.1/11.2	4037/1336/1297
54	1	0804480101	2017-12-30	35.6/45.4/45.1	373/154/151
55	1	0761590701	2015-06-20	18.7/-/22.4	680/-/251
56	1	0762520101	2016-01-13	26.8/36.2/35.9	1846/719/772
57	1	0782360201	2016-07-19	30.6/35.6/36.0	823/236/223
58	1	0803910101	2017-08-05	69.3/85.7/87.1	17087/5133/5637
59	1	0783520301	2016-08-26	-/60.9/60.9	-/153/144
60	1	0033540901	2002-01-06	11.4/15.3/15.2	1414/541/476
61	1	0153220601	2003-05-28	7.0/7.5/8.7	3975/1171/1301

Notes: (1) Unique X-HESS identifier; (2) Observation number; (3) *XMM-Newton* observation ID; (4) Start date of the observation; (5) Net exposure (in ks) for the pn/MOS1/MOS2 cameras, respectively; (6) net counts for the pn/MOS1/MOS2 cameras in the broad ($E = 0.3 - 10$ keV) observer-frame energy band.